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Correction: Melamine–terephthalaldehyde–lithium complex: a porous organic network based single ion electrolyte for lithium ion batteries

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Correction for 'Melamine–terephthalaldehyde–lithium complex: a porous organic network based single ion electrolyte for lithium ion batteries' by Rupesh Rohan *et al.*, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2015, 3, 5132–5139.

The authors regret that author 'Dan Zhao' was incorrectly listed as 'Zhao Dan'. The corrected author list is as above.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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